

Practice Abstract #1

Climate-Smart Land Management: Insights from the Italian Co-Creation Workshop

Summary

OBJECTIVES. On 30 May 2025, EARTHONE held a workshop in Legnaro (Italy) that brought together farmers, researchers, advisors and local organisations to identify practical needs for climate-smart land-use tools. Participants explored how the EARTHONE tools: Multi-Sensing Ecosystem (field sensing and monitoring), the Scenario Builder with AI support (what-if scenario testing with recommendations) and the Information Factory (collecting, storing, processing and sharing data) could help address drought, unpredictable rainfall and rising production costs.

RESULTS. Stakeholders confirmed that real-time soil and climate monitoring is highly valuable for daily farm decisions, particularly for irrigation and soil management. They stressed the need for low-cost, durable sensors and simple user interfaces. For the Scenario Builder, participants valued scenario comparison and AI recommendations but requested better localisation to farm conditions and the ability to adjust key variables. For the Information Factory, users highlighted the importance of a single, reliable platform combining climate, soil and market data supported by clear visualisation tools.

Figure 1. During the workshop in Legnaro

Farmers emphasised that tools must be simple, fast and mobile-friendly, with customisable dashboards and alerts. They also underlined the need for affordable monitoring options, clear data ownership rules, training adapted to different digital skill levels and the integration of economic factors such as crop prices and input costs. Tools should function with limited connectivity and integrate easily with existing farm systems.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS. The workshop showed strong willingness to adopt digital tools if they are easy to use, fairly priced and tailored to local conditions. Key barriers for the implementation include internet connectivity, sensor maintenance costs and data privacy concerns. Digital solutions should complement farmers' practical knowledge and support both environmental resilience and economic viability.

Additional information

Implementing climate-smart digital tools in agricultural and forestry settings depends strongly on local infrastructure and farmer engagement. It is also important to ensure the clarity of support measures. One key facilitating element identified during the Italian workshop is the presence of active farmer networks and advisory services capable of helping users navigate new technologies. Peer-to-peer exchange, producer associations, and regional technical bodies can play a decisive role in building trust and encouraging early adoption.

Figure 2. SWOT analysis

However, several obstacles may slow implementation. Many rural areas still face unstable connectivity, which limits the usability of tools requiring frequent data exchange. Another challenge is the diversity of farm structures: while larger holdings may integrate digital tools rapidly, small and family-run farms often require tailored guidance and lighter, modular solutions. Uncertainty surrounding the long-term maintenance of digital systems may also discourage investment.

Future research should test how digital recommendations perform under real operational conditions, comparing them with farmers' own strategies over multiple seasons. More work is also needed to ensure that tools reflect local agronomic knowledge, not only modelled scenarios. Integrating social and economic data such as labour availability and risk perception will help refine decision-support functions.

End-users are encouraged to approach digital tools gradually, starting with the features most relevant to their immediate needs. Engaging in training opportunities and collaborating with local advisory services can significantly improve results. The success of such tools will depend on transparent communication and long-term support frameworks ensuring that digital innovation strengthens the practical expertise already present within farming communities, instead of replacing it.

Useful links: [Blog - Italian stakeholders co-design EARTHONE tools](#)

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